

INTEGRATION PROCESSES IN THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Annotation: The article analyzes scientific approaches to the implementation of the principle of integration in the educational process of a preschool institution, formulates the reasons that complicate its successful implementation, in particular, related to the reorientation of teaching staff to other values and meanings of educational activities.

Key words: principle of integration, integration processes, educational process of a preschool institution.

Introduction. In the light of modern transformations, education is taking over a new sociocultural space, characterized by innovation and integration [3, 5]. It not only radically changes the forms, methods of teaching, and the realities of relationships between subjects of the educational process, it requires a fundamental update of the essence of the most important concepts and categories of pedagogical science [2, 4]. In particular, the concept of education today is associated with the process and result of illumination, the disclosure in the personality of each person of his most intimate, deepest essence, the formation of his image of his “I” [1]. This interpretation of the concept of “education” presupposes a fundamentally different methodology of the educational process, focused on other values, a different understanding of the role of the individual in learning, which, not only at the declarative level, but in reality should become not just a subject of learning in certain levels of education, but a subject of life activity. The main condition for this is knowledge, mastery of the achievements of human culture [6, 9, 10].

So, reflecting on the essence of innovative processes in modern education, we must first of all see them not in the content or technological aspects, which in themselves are also extremely important, but in the adoption of a new philosophy of education and the corresponding values and meanings, manifested in the construction of special relations between subjects of the educational process, each of them defining their progressive position and mission.

It is quite obvious that the main condition for real positive transformations is personnel, which, as we know, decide everything. It is important for educators to accept the essence of this humanistic educational philosophy with their hearts and minds and become imbued with it. At the same time, it is obvious that the current system of professional pedagogical training slows down the solution of this problem, therefore, mastering the “new rules of the game” falls on the shoulders of teaching staff of preschool institutions and each teacher separately [7, 8]. The process of content and technological renewal of modern preschool education is complicated by the lack of clear guidelines, the uncertainty of many of the parameters of the educational process, in particular terminological disagreements, didactic and methodological discrepancies, which shake the already restless boat of educational technologies [11].

A characteristic feature of pedagogical activity in the system of modern preschool education is a fairly high level of personal and professional activity of educators and methodologists, which indicates, first of all, their dissatisfaction with the existing level of the educational process, a sense of contradictions and an attempt to improve it meaningfully and technologically. After a long period of pressure from strict restrictions and instructions, most teachers sincerely try to self-realize, to achieve the heights of professional creativity and mastery, often, however, relying solely on their experience, knowledge and discretion [12, 13]. On the one hand, it seems joyful, but on the other, senseless and even alarming, that today almost every third educator is an innovator, a researcher, writes his own laws, and puts them into practice [14]. Increasingly, a situation is emerging where there is activity and even

tangible activity, often at the cost of the sheer enthusiasm of teachers, but there are no desired changes or improvements in overall educational results.

Scientists note that at the present stage, integrative trends in education are beginning to be implemented as laws. Consequently, awareness of the essence of integration processes in educational systems should proceed in the direction of awareness of the system of key concepts, axioms, postulates, and then laws. Let's turn to the analysis of key concepts. In order to clearly and unambiguously use the term integration, single-root concepts were analyzed [15]. The very concept of integration serves to designate the process or state of restoration through restoration, replenishment, and unification of previously isolated parts into a whole, that is, it means the result of integration or the action leading to this result. The term integrator means "factor", "reducer", "device for integration", integral means a holistic, unified, indivisible state associated with integration, or a specific way of cognition [17]. The concept of integrative means a process in which the external and internal, substantive and procedural aspects of integration are realized. Integrated means a holistic, externally defined state without internal contradictions, integration means a characteristic of a process implemented using integrative means. The word integration means the process of achieving integrity across elements. Integrate - complete integration actions [16].

The essence of the concept of "integration" most fully reflects the definition "Integration is the process of interaction of elements with given properties, accompanied by the establishment, complication and strengthening of significant connections between elements on the basis of a sufficient basis, as a result of which an integrated object (an integral system) with qualitatively new properties is formed, in the structure of which the individual properties of the original elements are preserved" [9, 18]. It is necessary to understand the essence of integration, because often in the organization of substantive or procedural aspects of the educational process, the conditions of integration are not fully met, therefore, integrative

formations are replaced only by those similar to them or have some of their characteristics.

Modern didactics distinguish between integral, integrated and integrative didactic systems, distinguished by the presence in the first group of systems of integral subsystems, which, unlike integrated ones, have more grounds for integration. Thus, if within integrated systems integration is subject only to a given goal (with virtually no regard for the nature of the elements of integration), then in integrated systems its elements are integrated taking into account the nature of these elements, determining the objective prerequisites for the integration process.

The integrative approach (as opposed to integrated or integrated) involves integration, both external and internal, both substantive and procedural. All elements of an integrative system are interconnected and form a certain structure (there may be several such structures depending on the purpose of forming the system). The main feature of such a system is that the content of educational material is determined not from the outside, but from the inside: the smallest elements form more complex subsystems, which, in turn, are combined into systems of a higher level of organization into problem blocks.

Certain elements of an integrated approach to organizing the educational process are embodied in the broad practice of preschool institutions, however, unfortunately, mainly only through integrated classes. However, it is also advisable to recommend the use of other forms of integration.

An integrated course can be built on the basis of combining knowledge on individual problems into integrated blocks, which creates the prerequisites for a comprehensive consideration of basic concepts, phenomena, a broader coverage of content, the formation of systematic thinking in children, a positive emotional attitude to knowledge, and also provides the opportunity for economical use educational time But it is very important in building an integrated course not to turn heterogeneous knowledge formally combined by external characteristics into a

mosaic. Such a course could be a system of integrated classes “Children’s Philosophy” or an integrated course “Creative Hours”.

Integrated classes are a form of educational work that combines blocks of knowledge from different areas around one topic in order to informationally and emotionally enrich the perception, thinking, and feelings of children, allowing them to understand a certain phenomenon from different angles and achieve the integrity of knowledge. The result of the systematic implementation of such activities is the formation of systematic thinking, stimulation of the imagination, and a positive emotional attitude towards the process of cognition.

Methodologists also offer integrative days - these are days the content of which is determined by a mega-theme, which involves going beyond the boundaries of one lesson for its most complete implementation. As a rule, integration days are associated with the inclusion of children in joint projective activities with adults, culminating in the achievement of a certain result.

Conclusions. An integrated approach to teaching certainly contributes to the expansion of children’s social and cognitive experience, the intensive development of cognitive processes, the formation of curiosity, and an active attitude towards events and phenomena of reality. Promotes the formation of personality in social relations and generally ensures preschool maturity. However, it should be remembered that the informativeness and attractiveness of the content of educational material does not in itself ensure the effectiveness of its assimilation and development of certain aspects of the preschooler’s personality. This requires a strategic vision of distant and immediate goals, a careful selection of means, methods and techniques of educational work in the structure of an integral didactic system.

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